

MATLAB code for "Alternative Procedures for Estimating Random Coefficient Logit Demand Models"

László Pál Zsolt Sándor

January 20, 2023

1 Software requirements

All the experiments were run under MATLAB 2014, and the central optimizer is KNITRO 10.0.1. In the case of BOBYQA, we use a C++ implementation from the Dlib open-source library (downloaded from <http://dlib.net>) through a Matlab MEX function. (Note that it may be necessary to regenerate the MEX file corresponding to the used Matlab version.) The Nelder-Mead algorithm is used from the NLOpt package through a MEX interface.

2 Script files

The script files are grouped in two different folders: *Code* and *Tables*. The *Code* folder contains the algorithms used in the paper. In all cases, the main script file must be run to obtain the results in the .mat files. Depending on the algorithms and scenarios, the .mat files should be placed in the Tables\Table_x\Algorithm_x folder. To obtain results for each individual algorithm, the run_all.m script should be run. For each Table_x the corresponding run_all.m script should run in order to get the final results in the *Results* folder.

References

- [1] Pál, L. and Sándor, Zs. (2023): "Alternative Procedures for Estimating Random Coefficient Logit Demand Models", *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, forthcoming.